

Student Research Project

Research Topic: Boosted Neural Networks for Tabular Regression

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15th March 2025

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I abstract

Tabular data represent one of the most prevalent forms of data in machine learning context. Despite recent advancements in using neural nets (NNs) to handle tabular data, there remains an active and ongoing debate about whether NNs outperform gradient-boosted decision trees (GBDTs) when examined with respect to tabular data, with some recent work suggesting either that GBDTs are consistently better than NNs or that NNs are consistently better than GBDTs. In this work, we attempt to bridge this gap by exploring various boosted neural network architectures on tabular data. We propose and evaluate three frameworks: Integrated Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles (NODE) with Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE), Boosted Fully Connected Networks (BFCN), and Boosted Residual Networks. Our experimental results reveal a mixed performance landscape for the proposed boosted neural network architectures when compared to established baselines. Against gradient-boosted decision trees, NODE+PLE demonstrates competitive performance primarily on regression tasks. However, significant underperformance is evident across classification tasks, with particularly poor results on HELOC and moderate performance on Adult Datasets. BFCN consistently underperforms GBDTs across all metrics, failing to achieve competitive results on any dataset. When evaluated against deep learning baselines, NODE+PLE shows more promising results, achieving state-of-the-art performance on California Housing regression and competitive accuracy on Adult classification. The results underscore the persistent challenge of achieving GBDT-level performance with neural architectures on tabular data, while simultaneously demonstrating that boosted neural networks can advance the state-of-the-art within the deep learning paradigm for specific dataset characteristics.

Keywords

Deep Learning (DL), Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles (NODE), Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE), Gradient-boosted decision trees (GBDTs), Boosted Dynamic Neural Networks (BoostNet)

Codebase: <https://www.uni-hildesheim.de/gitlab/srp-group>

Chapter 1

Introduction

I Motivation

Deep neural networks (DNNs) have achieved exceptional performance across a wide array of domains, including computer vision, natural language processing, and speech recognition, particularly when dealing with homogeneous data such as images, audio, and text [1, 8, 11]. However, their effectiveness on heterogeneous tabular data remains a significant and persistent challenge [14, 46, 37]. Tabular data, unlike image or language data, is inherently heterogeneous, often comprising a mix of dense numerical and sparse categorical features, with correlations among these features typically weaker and more irregular [7]. This challenge is critical because tabular data represents the most commonly used form of data and is indispensable for numerous vital and computationally demanding applications [3, 7, 46].

Despite the proven success of DNNs in other domains, gradient-boosted decision trees (GBDTs), such as XGBoost [9], LightGBM [27], and CatBoost [38], still largely outperform deep learning models on supervised learning tasks involving tabular data [7]. This indicates a potential stagnation in research progress for competitive deep learning models in this domain [7]. Empirical comparisons often show that GBDTs offer superior accuracy, training efficiency, inference speed, and hyperparameter optimization time [7]. There is an active debate on whether neural networks or GBDTs generally outperform each other on tabular data, with various works arguing for [4, 26, 30, 36, 41] or against [7, 20, 21, 46] NNs. However, McElfresh et al. [32] reported that this "NN vs. GBDT" debate may be overemphasized, as for a significant number of datasets, either the performance difference is

negligible, or light hyperparameter tuning on a GBDT is more impactful than the choice between NN and GBDT.

Nevertheless, deep neural networks possess several inherent advantages that make their adaptation to tabular data a compelling research direction. DNNs are highly flexible [42], allow for efficient and iterative training, and are particularly valuable in AutoML contexts [23, 45]. Furthermore, neural networks can be deployed for multimodal learning problems where tabular data serves as one input modality [45], for tabular data distillation [33, 31], and in federated learning scenarios [40].

Given the persistent performance gap and the unique characteristics of tabular data, this project aims to bridge the divide by exploring and enhancing boosted neural network frameworks for tabular data prediction. The core idea is to investigate how an ensemble approach to modeling neural networks can adapt the strengths of traditional tree-boosted models to achieve improved predictive performance.

I.1 Problem Setting

Given a dataset $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ and corresponding labels $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$, where N represents the number of training instances and M represents the number of input features. Let $\ell : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a loss function, and $f_{\theta} : \mathbb{R}^M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ represent a neural network parameterized by learnable parameters θ .

Our objective is to find the optimal parameter vector θ^* that minimizes the empirical risk:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta) = \arg \min_{\theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}, f_{\theta}(\mathbf{X}))$$

where $f_{\theta}(\mathbf{X}) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represents the network’s predictions over all training instances, and θ encompasses all trainable parameters including weights and biases across all layers of the neural network.

The loss function is defined for different task types by the following:

Regression: Mean Squared Error (MSE) is applied

$$L_{\text{MSE}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (y_j - \hat{y}_j)^2.$$

Binary Classification: Binary Cross-Entropy Loss

$$L_{\text{BCE}} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n [y_j \log \hat{y}_j + (1 - y_j) \log(1 - \hat{y}_j)].$$

Multiclass classification: Cross-Entropy Loss

$$L_{\text{CE}} = -\sum_{j=1}^n y_j \log \hat{y}_j$$

I.2 Research Idea

Gradient boosting techniques, particularly models like XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost, have become the established standard for tabular data prediction, consistently achieving state-of-the-art performance [7, 32]. This stands in contrast to the exceptional performance of deep neural networks (DNNs) in other homogeneous data domains such as computer vision and natural language processing [48, 18]. The effectiveness of DNNs on heterogeneous tabular data, which often consists of a mix of dense numerical and sparse categorical features with weaker and more irregular correlations, remains a significant challenge [43, 52, 48]. Indeed, tabular datasets have been called the "last unconquered castle" for deep neural network models [7]. While the "NN vs. GBDT" debate can be overemphasized for many datasets where performance differences are negligible or hyperparameter tuning is more impactful, GBDTs are generally better at handling skewed or heavy-tailed feature distributions and other data irregularities, and tend to perform better on larger datasets [32].

This project is grounded in the hypothesis that employing neural networks within a boost-like structure can enhance their predictive accuracy on tabular datasets. Specifically, we propose to investigate the possibility of combining structured feature engineering, such as Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) [19], with hierarchical, boost-like learning principles through neural networks. We aspire to explore how a thoughtful combination of neural networks in a consecutive boosting format can adapt the strengths of traditional tree-boosted models, aiming for improved predictive performance over conventional methods for tabular data prediction. The ultimate goal is to demonstrate that architectures employing these boosted neural network frameworks could potentially surpass the performance of both traditional GBDTs and standalone deep neural networks, offering versatile and potentially interpretable solutions for complex tabular data challenges.

I.3 Objective

The primary objective of this study is to explore and advance the use of boosted neural network techniques for tabular data prediction. To achieve this, we define the following goals:

- Conduct a thorough review of recent advancements in boosted neural network architectures and ensemble strategies.
- Reproduce and validate the reported results of these approaches to establish a reliable baseline.
- Adapt the identified neural network architectures specifically for tabular data applications where applicable.
- Benchmark and evaluate the adapted models against state-of-the-art gradient-boosted tree algorithms as well as existing neural network baselines.
- Enhance model performance through structured feature engineering and optimization of ensemble configurations.
- Analyze the resulting performance to develop a deeper understanding of the suitability, strengths, and limitations of boosted neural networks for tabular data.

Chapter 2

Related Works

The concept of boosting, an ensemble algorithm that combines multiple weak learners into a single strong learner has significantly influenced predictive performance on tabular data. This section reviews the foundational gradient boosted decision tree models and the main neural architectures that inform our approach, by considering the models that incorporate boosting-inspired methodologies [32]

I The Boosting Framework

The algorithmic foundation for boosting was established with the AdaBoost (Adaptive Boosting) algorithm by Freund & Schapire [16]. AdaBoost works by adaptively changing the weights of training instances, making subsequent weak learners (e.g., decision stumps) to focus on previously misclassified examples. This concept was expanded by Friedman [17] with the introduction to gradient boosting by modeling it as a numerical optimization problem in function space. In this, the model is built sequentially in a greedy, stage-wise manner where each new learner is trained to minimize the loss by correcting the errors of its predecessors. The core idea is to iteratively add weak learners to an ensemble, with each new model trained to predict the negative gradients (the "pseudo-residuals") of the current ensemble's loss.

Formally, given a differentiable loss function $\mathcal{L}(y, F(x))$, the gradient boosting algorithm proceeds as follows [17]

1. **Initialize the model with a constant value:**

$$F_0(x) = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{L}(y_i, \gamma) \quad (2.1)$$

2. **For** $m = 1$ **to** M (number of boosting rounds), perform the following steps:

(a) **Compute the pseudo-residuals for each instance i :**

$$r_i^{(m)} = - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)} \right]_{F(x)=F_{m-1}(x)} \quad (2.2)$$

This equation defines the “error” that the new weak learner must fit.

(b) **Fit a weak learner** $h_m(x)$ (e.g., a decision tree) to the pseudo-residuals $\{r_i^{(m)}\}$.

(c) **Find the optimal step size γ_m via line search:**

$$\gamma_m = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{L}(y_i, F_{m-1}(x_i) + \gamma h_m(x_i)) \quad (2.3)$$

(d) **Update the model:**

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \nu \cdot \gamma_m h_m(x) \quad (2.4)$$

Here, $\nu \in (0, 1]$ is the *shrinkage* or *learning rate*, a hyperparameter that controls the contribution of each weak learner to prevent overfitting. [17]

II Gradient-Boosted Decision Trees (GBDTs)

GBDT models form the baselines for any research on tabular data regression. These models build an ensemble of decision trees iteratively, and correct the errors made by the existing ensemble of trees. Each new tree is trained to model the gradient of the loss function. [32] Gradient-boosted decision tree (GBDT) models such as XGBoost [9], LightGBM [27], and CatBoost [38] are well known for their robust performance, efficiency, and ability to handle heterogeneous features which made them dominate the area of tabular data prediction.

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is an implementation of the gradient boosting framework that enhances the core GBDT algorithm through a second-order approximation of the loss function for more efficient boosting, regularization (L1/L2) to prevent overfitting, and a sparsity-aware algorithm that efficiently handles missing values. It learns the best direction to send a data point with a missing value at each split, allowing it to process sparse data without expensive preprocessing [9].

LightGBM [27] is also a framework of GBDT models designed to handle the computation and memory limitations of models like the XGboost when applied to very large datasets. Its innovation is based on two main techniques being the Gradient-based one-sided sampling(GOSS) and Exclusive Feature Bundling(EFB)[27].The traditional boosting uses every data point to evaluate splits, which is expensive on large datasets but with GOSS , it keeps all instances with large gradients and randomly samples from those with small gradients. EFB reduces the number of features while maintaining significant information. It identifies mutually exclusive features and bundles them into a single feature. Integrating these techniques results in a decreased memory usage and faster training speed.[27]

CatBoost(categorical boosting) [38] is a variant of GBDT which uses the strategy of ordered boosting that calculates the statistics for a categorical feature for a given training example using only the historical data that appeared before it in a random permutation. It addresses the issue of target leakage that leads to prediction shift when handling categorical features. This GBDT model is more effective on datasets rich in categorical data.[38]

III Boosted Neural Network Architectures

Despite the strengths of these GBDTs models, they are not without limitations. They require careful feature engineering[27], can sometimes struggle with extrapolation in regression tasks, and their non-differentiable nature makes its integration into larger deep-learning pipelines challenging[36] The exploration of deep learning models has become an active area of research[32] and the idea of leveraging their capacity for hierarchical representation learning and end-to-end differentiability[32]. An aspect within this exploration is the fusion of deep learning with the principles of boosting, creating ensemble structures where neural networks act as weak learners.[10] [5] [24] [50]

ADANET

This research proposes adaptive learning algorithms for neural network structures and their corresponding weights, starting from a simple linear model. The algorithms incrementally build the architecture’s complexity, guided by data-dependent generalization guarantees. This unique approach averts the difficulties associated with pre-specifying network architectures and facilitates the learning of a suitable structure for a given task. $\phi(x)$ being a

non-increasing convex function and $x \mapsto \mathbf{1}_{x \leq 0}$, such that ϕ is differentiable over \mathbb{R} and $\phi'(x) \neq 0$ for all x . This loss ϕ may be, for instance, the exponential function $\phi(x) = e^x$ as in AdaBoost[16], or the logistic function $\phi(x) = \log(1 + e^x)$ as in logistic regression. The objective function is defined by $\{h_1, \dots, h_N\}$ being a subset of \mathcal{H}^* . In the most general case, N is infinite. But in practice the search is limited to a finite set, for any $j \in [N]$ and they denote by r_j the Rademacher complexity of the family \mathcal{H}_j^k that contains h_j :

$$r_j = \mathfrak{R}_m(\mathcal{H}_j^k).$$

ADANET seeks to find a function

$$f = \sum_{j=1}^N w_j h_j \in \mathcal{F}^*$$

which leads to the objective function:

$$F(w) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \phi \left(1 - y_i \sum_{j=1}^N w_j h_j \right) + \sum_{j=1}^N \lambda_j |w_j|, \quad (4)$$

where $w \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and $\lambda_j = \tau r_j + \gamma$, with $\tau \geq 0$ and $\gamma \geq 0$ hyperparameters.

The objective function (4) is a convex function of w . It is the sum of a convex surrogate of the empirical error and a regularization term, which is a weighted ℓ_1 penalty containing two sub-terms: a standard ℓ_1 regularization (controlled by γ) and a term that discriminates the functions h_j based on their complexity. [10]

Figure 2.1: ADANET’s incremental construction of a neural network. The input layer is indicated in blue, the output layer in green. Units in the yellow block are added at the first iteration while units in purple are added at the second iteration. Two candidate extensions of the architecture are considered at the third iteration (shown in red): (a) a two-layer extension; (b) a three-layer extension. Here, a line between two blocks of units indicates that these blocks are fully-connected [10]

Gradient Boosting Neural Networks (GrowNet)

This research combines gradient boost with shallow neural networks in a general framework that is innovative in producing robust results in various learning tasks. This model incorporates corrective steps into the boosting process. The prediction for an input x_i is provided by the additive ensemble of K functions (shallow neural networks) that makes up GrowNet’s architecture; where the prediction for an input x_i is given by: [5]

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=0}^K \alpha_k f_k(x_i), \quad f_k \in \mathcal{F}. \quad (2.5)$$

There are two main innovations in its training process. First, it uses second-order gradient statistics to fit each new weak learner. For a loss function l , at stage t , it computes the first-order gradient g_i and second-order gradient h_i of $l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)})$ with respect to the current prediction. The next weak learner f_t is then trained to solve a weighted least-squares regression problem: [5]

$$L^{(t)} = \sum_{i=0}^n h_i (\tilde{y}_i - f_t(x_i))^2, \quad \text{where} \quad \tilde{y}_i = -\frac{g_i}{h_i}. \quad (2.6)$$

Second, GrowNet incorporates a fully corrective step (C/S). After adding f_t , it performs a global refinement by updating the parameters of all existing weak learners $\{f_0, \dots, f_t\}$ through backpropagation, directly minimizing the original task loss l in the raw inputs. The model improves the transfer of information between stages by data augmentation where for each weak learner after the first, the input feature vector x_i is concatenated with the activations from the penultimate layer of the previous weak learner. This allows each subsequent network to build on richer and more abstract representations than the residual alone. [5]

Figure 2.2: Gradient Boosting Neural Network Architecture

Boosted Dynamic Neural Networks

Early-Exiting Dynamic Neural Networks (EDNNs) represents a class of adaptive inference models that employ multiple prediction heads distributed across different layers of a network backbone. These architectures enable computational efficiency by allowing early termination when prediction confidence exceeds predefined thresholds or computational budgets are met. However, a fundamental limitation emerges from the train-test mismatch problem: during training, all classifiers are optimized on the entire training dataset, while during inference, deeper classifiers predominantly process difficult samples after easier inputs have been handled by shallower exits.

Yu et al. [50] addressed this distributional discrepancy through the introduction of Boosted Dynamic Neural Networks (BoostNet), a framework inspired by gradient boosting theory that formulates dynamic neural networks as additive models. The key insight lies in treating each classifier as a weak learner that corrects the residual errors of its predecessors, thereby aligning the training process more closely with the intended inference behavior.

The BoostNet architecture consists of N sequential blocks, where each block n contains a feature extraction component $f_n(x)$ and an associated

classifier F_n . The network backbone can be instantiated using existing dynamic architectures such as MSDNet [25] or RANet [49], both designed for adaptive inference scenarios. The fundamental architectural principle revolves around additive ensemble construction, where the final prediction at block n is formulated as:

$$F_n(x) = t_n \cdot F_{n-1}(x) + f_n(x) \quad (2.7)$$

where t_n represents a temperature parameter that modulates the contribution of previous classifiers, effectively implementing a prediction reweighting mechanism.

Figure 2.3: Architecture of Boosted Dynamic Neural Networks

The training methodology incorporates three critical components to address the inherent challenges of dynamic network optimization. First, joint optimization ensures that all classifiers are trained simultaneously rather than sequentially, preventing the degradation of earlier classifiers when deeper ones are added. The overall loss function is constructed as a weighted sum across all classifiers:

$$L(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N L_n(\text{stop-grad}(F_{n-1}(x)) + f_n(x), y) \quad (2.8)$$

The $\text{stop-grad}()$ operation prevents gradient flow from deeper losses to earlier ensemble predictions, maintaining the independence assumption required for effective boosting behavior.

Second, prediction reweighting through temperature scaling addresses the diminishing effective training data problem for deeper classifiers. By setting $t_n = 0.5$ across all layers, the influence of previous predictions is systematically reduced, forcing deeper classifiers to focus on correcting residual errors rather than simply learning from already well-classified examples. This mechanism ensures that deeper layers receive sufficient challenging training samples to develop meaningful representations.

Third, gradient rescaling, adapted from techniques proposed by Li et al. [22], bounds the magnitude of gradients flowing through different network branches. The gradient of the overall loss with respect to block b_n is rescaled as:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial b_n} = \frac{1}{N - n + 1} \sum_{i=n}^N \frac{\partial L_i}{\partial b_n} \quad (2.9)$$

This rescaling operation ensures balanced learning across all depth levels and prevents gradient explosion in deeper layers, which is particularly important when training networks with many exit points.

The experimental validation on CIFAR-100 and ImageNet datasets demonstrates significant improvements over baseline MSDNet and RANet architectures in both anytime and budgeted-batch prediction modes. The performance gains are particularly pronounced under low computational budgets, where the corrective nature of the boosting framework provides substantial benefits. The method achieves state-of-the-art results while maintaining the adaptive inference capabilities essential for resource-constrained deployment scenarios.

Boosted ResNet Architecture

BoostResNet reframes the ResNet architecture through a novel boosting lens by constructing a multichannel telescoping sum boosting framework: the network is viewed as an ensemble of T weak module classifiers [44], each comprising a shallow ResNet block paired with an auxiliary linear classifier. [24] These are trained sequentially, and the ensemble collectively constitutes a deep ResNet via a telescoping sum identity that matches the standard ResNet output. [24] Under a weak learning condition, where each module performs just slightly better than a baseline, the training error decays exponentially with depth, reinforcing strong performance as the network deepens. Overall, BoostResNet offers a theoretically grounded, computationally efficient alternative to end-to-end training, especially advantageous in non-differentiable contexts. [24]

The starting point of their architecture is the standard ResNet formulation, where each hidden representation is updated according to

$$h_{t+1}(x) = h_t(x) + f_t(h_t(x)),$$

with $h_t(x)$ denoting the hidden state at layer t , and f_t the residual mapping learned by the block. The final classifier is then applied to the representation

at the last layer,

$$F(x) = w^\top h_T(x),$$

where w is the linear classifier attached to the output of the final block.

BoostResNet modifies this by decomposing the network into weak module classifiers. Each module consists of a residual block f_t paired with its own linear classifier w_t . Formally, the module classifier at step t is defined as

$$o_t(x) = w_t^\top h_t(x),$$

where $h_t(x)$ is the output of the residual mapping at that stage. The final prediction of the network is then represented as a telescoping sum of these module classifiers:

$$F(x) = \sum_{t=0}^T \alpha_t o_t(x),$$

with coefficients α_t chosen such that the ensemble exactly reconstructs the standard ResNet output [24].

To support the theory, Huang et al. (2018) conduct extensive experiments on CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and SVHN. The results show that BoostResNet “achieves test performance comparable to that of end-to-end ResNet training” while requiring substantially less GPU memory (p. 2065). Because the method trains blocks sequentially, only one shallow block needs to be loaded into memory at a time, making it efficient for very deep architectures. The experiments also confirm the theoretical predictions: as the number of modules increases, training error decreases steadily, and test accuracy improves correspondingly. Overall, BoostResNet offers a theoretically grounded reinterpretation of residual networks by formalizing them as a boosting ensemble, with a telescoping-sum representation that preserves the ResNet output. Its sequential training procedure provides both computational savings and provable convergence guarantees, positioning it as a unique contribution in the literature on deep residual learning.

Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles(NODE)

Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles, is a deep learning architecture that combines the strengths of tree-based models and deep neural networks. Its main innovation is the creation of a differentiable ensemble of oblivious decision trees (ODTs), that makes end-to-end training via gradient descent possible.[36] An Oblivious Decision Tree (ODT) is a type of decision tree that has all nodes at the same depth and must use the same feature and the

same threshold for splitting. For a tree of depth d this homogeneity transforms the tree from a standard branching structure into a decision table with 2^d entries, where each entry represents a unique combination of binary decisions. While this constraint reduces the capacity of a single tree, it makes ensembles of ODTs highly efficient for inference and remarkably resistant to overfitting. [36] The CatBoost algorithm [38], uses ODTs as weak learners in gradient boosting and this has contributed significantly to its success [38] This idea is expanded upon in the NODE architecture. Several differentiable ODTs make up a NODE layer. The key to differentiability lies in replacing the hard, non-differentiable operations of a standard decision tree (feature selection and binary routing) with soft, learnable alternatives: The NODE architecture generalizes ensembles of Oblivious Decision Trees(ODTs) into a fully differentiable framework that can be trained end-to-end via gradient descent. An ODT is a decision tree where all nodes at a given depth d use the same feature and threshold for splitting, effectively forming a decision table. [36] For the differentiable ODT, in a single NODE layer, there are m differentiable ODTs and the forward pass for one tree is built to approximate the function of a classical ODT while maintaining differentiability. In a classical ODT, the non-differentiable output is given by:

$$h(x) = R[\mathbf{1}(f_1(x) - b_1), \mathbf{1}(f_2(x) - b_2), \dots, \mathbf{1}(f_d(x) - b_d)] \quad (2.10)$$

where $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function, f_i is the selected feature at the i -th split, b_i is the corresponding threshold, and R is a d -dimensional response tensor that holds the leaf values. To allow differentiability, NODE replaces these hard operations with soft, learnable alternatives. The hard selection of a single feature f_i is replaced by a sparse, weighted combination of all features using the α -entmax transformation [35] applied to a learnable feature selection matrix $F \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times n}$:

$$\hat{f}_i(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \cdot \text{entmax}_\alpha(F_{ij}) \quad (2.11)$$

Here, $\alpha = 1.5$ is used to induce sparsity, ensuring the output closely mimics a hard feature selection. The classical Heaviside step function is replaced by a scaled, two-class variant of entmax, defined as:

$$\sigma_\alpha(x) = \text{entmax}_\alpha([x, 0]) \quad (2.12)$$

The soft routing probability for the i -th split is then:

$$c_i(x) = \sigma_\alpha\left(\frac{f_i(x) - b_i}{\tau_i}\right), \quad (2.13)$$

where b_i and τ_i are learnable scaling parameters. The value $c_i(x) \in [0, 1]$ represents the soft probability of taking the right branch at the i -th split. The final tree output is computed as a weighted sum over all leaves. The weights are given by the outer product of the soft choice vectors for all d splits, forming a "choice tensor" $C(x)$:

$$C(x) = \begin{bmatrix} c_1(x) \\ 1 - c_1(x) \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} c_2(x) \\ 1 - c_2(x) \end{bmatrix} \otimes \dots \otimes \begin{bmatrix} c_d(x) \\ 1 - c_d(x) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.14)$$

The final prediction of a single tree is:

$$\hat{h}(x) = \sum_{i_1, \dots, i_d \in \{0,1\}^d} R_{i_1, \dots, i_d} \cdot C_{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x) \quad (2.15)$$

The output of a NODE layer is the concatenation of the outputs of all m trees:

$$[\hat{h}_1(x), \hat{h}_2(x), \dots, \hat{h}_m(x)]$$

Figure 2.4: Architecture of a single differentiable Oblivious Decision Tree (ODT) within a NODE layer. The single ODT inside the NODE layer. The splitting features and the splitting thresholds are shared across all the internal nodes of the same depth. The output is a sum of leaf responses scaled by the choice weights [36]

Multi-Layer Hierarchical Architecture Several NODE layers stacked in a denseNet-like fashion forms the full NODE model [51] where each layer uses a concatenation of all previous layers. so, the input to the k -th layer is a concatenation of the original input features and the outputs from all previous layers 0 to $k - 1$. Due to this design, the model is able to learn hierarchical feature interactions, where trees in deeper layers can learn complex rules

based on high-level representations extracted by earlier layers. The final prediction is computed as the average of the outputs from all trees across all NODE layers:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{h}_k(x) \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.5: The multi-layer NODE architecture with DenseNet-style feature reuse across layers. The NODE architecture, consisting of densely connected NODE layers. Each layer contains several trees whose outputs are concatenated and serve as input for the subsequent layer. The final prediction is obtained by averaging the outputs of all trees from all the layers [36].

On Embeddings for Numerical Features in Tabular Deep Learning

This research introduced an underexplored domain of deep learning (DL) for tabular data being the embedding of numerical features. The authors introduce two approaches for constructing embeddings for numerical features: Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) and Periodic Activation (P) functions. [19] The PLE method is inspired by classical feature binning techniques, where the value range of a numerical feature is divided into intervals (bins), and the feature values are encoded in a piecewise linear manner. The results of the research demonstrate that the technique helps to improve the performance of deep learning models on tabular data. This approach allows simple MLP models to compete with more complex Transformer-based models. They also show that the integration of this approach into the deep learning pipeline produces state-of-the-art results on tabular Deep Learning closing the performance gap with GBDTs. [19]

Piecewise Linear Encoding(PLE):

The design of PLE is motivated by the limitations of deep learning for tabular data. While Multilayer Perceptrons are known to be a universal approximator [24] [19], their learning capabilities in practice are often hampered by optimization difficulties [39] [19]. Recent work by Tancik et al. [47] demonstrated that transforming the input space can significantly solve these optimization issues. This finding directly inspires the core premise of PLE: that altering the representation of original scalar numerical feature values can enhance the learning capabilities of tabular deep learning models [16]. The authors use the one-hot encoding algorithm, a method that is wildly successful for representing discrete entities (e.g., categorical features, NLP tokens) [19]. The one-hot representation sits at the opposite end of the spectrum from a scalar representation in the trade-off between parameter efficiency and expressivity [19]. To test if a one-hot-like approach could benefit deep learning models on numerical data, PLE is designed as a continuous alternative to one-hot encoding, making it applicable to numerical features. [16] [19]

For a given numerical feature x , PLE defines T bins(intervals) with boundaries b_0, b_1, \dots, b_T . The encoding transforms the scalar value x into a T -dimensional vector [19] where the t -th element(bin) is calculated as:

$$e_t = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x < b_{t-1} \text{ and } t > 1, \\ 1, & \text{if } x \geq b_t \text{ and } t < T, \\ \frac{x - b_{t-1}}{b_t - b_{t-1}}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The full PLE encoding vector is:

$$\text{PLE}(x) = [e_1, e_2, \dots, e_T],$$

Figure 2.6: The Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) in action for $T = 4$ [19]. The scalar input value x is mapped to a 4-dimensional vector $[e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4]$ based on its position within the bins, creating a structured and interpretable representation.

The authors rely on the classic binning algorithms [12] and one of the two algorithms is unsupervised, while another one utilizes labels for constructing bins. **Obtaining bins from quantiles (Unsupervised Binning):** A natural baseline way to construct the bins is by splitting value ranges according to uniformly chosen empirical quantiles of the corresponding individual feature distributions [PLEPaper]:

$$b_t = q_{\frac{t}{T}} \left(\{x_i^j\} \right) \quad \text{for } j \in \text{training set.}$$

Trivial bins of zero size are removed. **Supervised Target-aware Binning (Building target-aware bins):** This supervised approach employs training labels for constructing bins, identical in spirit to the C4.5 Discretization [29] algorithm [19]. For each feature, we recursively split its value range in a greedy manner using the target as guidance. This is equivalent to building a decision tree (which uses for growing only this one feature and the target) and treating the regions corresponding to its leaves as the bins for PLE [19]. we define

$$b_0^i = \min_{j \in J_{\text{train}}} x_i^j \quad \text{and} \quad b_T^i = \max_{j \in J_{\text{train}}} x_i^j [?].$$

Periodic Activation Function(P)

This design projects scalar values into a periodic space using learnable frequencies. [47] For this method, a feature x , the embedding is constructed as:

$$f_i(x) = \text{Periodic}(x) = \text{concat}[\sin(v), \cos(v)], \quad (2.17)$$

where

$$v = [2\pi c_1 x, 2\pi c_2 x, \dots, 2\pi c_k x], \quad (2.18)$$

and c_i are trainable parameters initialized from a normal distribution

$$c_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma). \quad (2.19)$$

The hyperparameters σ (initial frequency scale) and k (number of frequencies) are crucial and are tuned on the validation set.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This project aims to bridge the performance gap between deep learning models and Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDTs) on heterogeneous tabular data. To achieve this, we explore advanced concepts of:

- Integrating a deep learning architecture that mimics tree ensembles and introducing a novel method for representing numerical features into this architecture. The core of our methodology is the integration of Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) into the Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles (NODE) architecture, creating a powerful and differentiable model for tabular regression and classification.
- Adapting deep neural network models to be more comparative with gradient boosting decision tree models(GBDTs) on heterogenous tabular data.

I Integrated NODE + PLE Architecture

The integration of the piecewise linear encoding(PLE)for numerical embeddings with the Neural Oblivious Decision Ensembles(NODE) architecture is an innovation of this work with the aim of addressing the limitations of deep learning on tabular data. While the components are powerful individually, we believe their combination will result in a more robust model.

The integrated architecture leverages the strengths of both NODE and PLE to process data. The PLE model processes each numerical feature x_i separately by its own PLE module. Based on the chosen strategy (unsupervised PLE or supervised), the scalar value is transformed into a high-dimensional, piecewise-linear representation $\text{PLE}(x_i) \in \mathbb{R}^T$. This vector is then passed

through a feature-specific linear layer to obtain a final dense embedding [37]:

$$e_i^{\text{num}} = W_i \cdot \text{PLE}(x_i) + b_i.$$

Each categorical feature is processed through a standard embedding layer, mapping each category to a dense vector e_j^{cat} . All resulting numerical embeddings e_i^{num} and categorical embeddings e_j^{cat} are concatenated to form a joint, rich input representation vector z . The vector z is fed into the multi-layer NODE architecture [37]. The differentiable oblivious decision trees within each NODE layer now operate on this pre-enriched embedding space rather than on raw, normalized scalars. The DenseNet-like structure allows subsequent layers to use the transformed, high-level features learned by earlier layers, enabling the learning of complex hierarchical interactions between the PLE-encoded features. The final output is a simple average of the outputs from all trees across all NODE layers.

Figure 3.1: Architecture of Integrated NODE + PLE. from the top left, input features are encoded via Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE). All embeddings are concatenated and processed by a multi-layer NODE architecture, which learns hierarchical interactions through its ensembles of differentiable oblivious decision trees. The final prediction is an average of all tree outputs [37]

Why PLE for NODE Integration

The choice of Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) over other embeddings for integration with NODE is due to a shared inductive bias. Both methods are fundamentally based on the concept of splitting data on feature thresholds. This is the core operational principle that makes tree-based models like

Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDTs) powerful on tabular data. NODE explicitly mimics this principle by constructing a differentiable ensemble of oblivious decision trees that learn differentiable splits. PLE directly encodes this principle into the input representation. It transforms a scalar value into a vector based on its position within learned bins (or intervals), defined by thresholds

$$(b_0, b_1, \dots, b_T).$$

Therefore, PLE provides an input signal that is already structured in the form that NODE is designed to understand. The tree-like output of PLE is a fit for the tree-based learning of NODE, creating a more powerful and aligned model than with other, less compatible embeddings.

Why This Combination is Innovative

Previous attempts to make deep learning competitive with GBDTs focused primarily on designing novel backbone architectures (e.g., Transformers[48, 20], other attention mechanisms) or on creating completely differentiable tree structures (e.g., NODE[37]). This work is unique by focusing on the critical but underexplored *input representation layer* for numerical features. Innovation lies in recognizing that:

- The input representation (simple scalars) is a key bottleneck.
- A technique (PLE) exists to create a much richer representation.
- A specific architecture (NODE) exists that is perfectly suited to exploit this richer representation due to its tree-like nature.

By integrating PLE with NODE, we aim to create a unified architecture that directly addresses the core weaknesses of Deep Neural Networks on tabular data, pushing their performance closer to and beyond that of state-of-the-art GBDTs

II Boosted Fully Connected Networks (BFCN)

A concerted attempt was made to extend the advantages of dynamic inference to heterogeneous tabular data by integrating the Boosted Dynamic Neural Network (BoostNet) model into a fully-connected network framework, which will be referred to as **Boosted Fully Connected Networks (BFCN)**. This modification was essential for resolving the well-known issues that deep neural networks encounter when working with tabular datasets,

where gradient-boosted decision trees (GBDTs) have historically outperformed them. The approach concentrated on particular functional and architectural changes to BoostNet, which was first created for image classification, in order to guarantee its effectiveness and resilience in a variety of tabular tasks. The adapted code is available for use at [BFCN Repository](#). A primary step in this integration involved reimagining the network backbone for tabular data. The original BoostNet implementation, which utilized convolutional layers for image data in architectures like MSDNet [25] and RANet [49], was fundamentally unsuited for tabular inputs due to their lack of spatial dependencies. Consequently, these convolutional structures were replaced with linear (fully connected) layers to effectively process the distinct features inherent in tabular data. For instance, *TabularMSDNFirstLayer*, *TabularMSDNLayer*, and *TabularClassifierModule* were developed as linear equivalents for the MSDNet backbone, forming the *TabularMSDNet*. Similarly, *LinearBasic*, *LinearBN*, and *LinearUpNormal* components were implemented to construct the *TabularRANet* for its respective backbone, enabling these dynamic network architectures to operate on tabular inputs. To provide the multi-block boosted training functionality, a cornerstone of the BoostNet model, a dynamic network wrapper was meticulously implemented and configured within the tabular pipeline. This wrapper included *DynamicNet* for *TabularMSDNet* and *DynamicRANet* for *TabularRANet*, ensuring that the core BoostNet design of sequentially refined blocks and ensemble predictions was fully realized for tabular data. This aligned the tabular implementation with the theoretical framework of BoostNet, where deeper classifiers are supplementary to their predecessors, learning to correct mistakes and focus on more challenging inputs. The framework was further enhanced to properly process the *ensemble_reweight* parameter, adjusting the influence of earlier blocks' predictions on later ones, consistent with BoostNet's original prediction reweighting strategy.

A significant **expansion of capabilities** included comprehensive support for **regression tasks** and **binary classification**, which were not the primary focus of the original BoostNet paper, largely centered on multi-class image classification datasets like CIFAR100 and ImageNet. The integrated framework was designed to automatically detect whether a task was classification or regression. For regression, targets are **automatically normalized using** *StandardScaler* to prevent gradient explosion, *torch.nn.MSELoss()* is employed as the primary optimization metric, and evaluation metrics were expanded to include Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and R² score, replacing the classification-centric accuracy and AUC metrics. The adapted *TabularMS-*

DNet and *TabularRANet* architectures were made fully compatible with both classification (including binary and multi-class) and regression tasks, with the output layer dynamically configured with a single neuron for regression. This broadens the applicability of BoostNet’s principles to a wider array of real-world tabular problems beyond image domains.

The training methodology adopted the BoostNet approach, utilizing **mini-batch joint optimization** over all classifiers (blocks), where the total loss is a weighted sum of individual block losses. The crucial prediction reweighting strategy with a temperature parameter (tn) was applied to the output of preceding classifiers (F_{n-1}) before combination with the current classifier’s output (f_n), allowing for dynamic adjustment of contribution and emphasizing error correction in deeper layers. The *stop-grad* function was also implemented for $F_{n-1}(x)$ to prevent gradients from directly affecting previous layers, ensuring that each new block primarily learns residuals from the previous ensemble. Furthermore, gradient rescaling was applied, similar to the original BoostNet, to bound gradients from different network branches, contributing to balanced learning across layers. These elements collectively ensured that the enhanced training techniques of BoostNet were fully operational and beneficial for tabular data.

Finally, several critical issues specific to tabular integration were identified and resolved to establish robust functionality. This included fixing a *num_features* initialization mismatch in the evaluation script, which previously led to dimension errors during model loading by not correctly reflecting the dataset’s actual feature count. A **checkpoint metadata system** was implemented to store comprehensive training configurations, enabling intelligent loading of parameters before model and dataloader creation in evaluation scripts. Other resolved issues encompassed evaluation script stability, model architecture mismatches due to inconsistent parameter loading, proper handling of string labels in categorical features, and the addition of dataset compatibility guards. These comprehensive modifications ensure that the powerful multi-block boosted training, characteristic of BoostNet, is robustly extended to both tabular classification and regression domains.

III Boosted Residual Networks

Based on the framework proposed by Huang et al., which was originally designed for image classification, methodology first adapts the algorithm to work with tabular data. Rather than a typical ResNet algorithm, the

concept of residual learning in combination with boosting is used here. The architecture is based on boosting a sequence of residual blocks with each subsequent block refining the errors of the previous ones. This approach trains neural networks as an ensemble of weak learners, mimicking boosting, where each weak learner is a ResNet block.

Input Layer takes raw tabular data and process it before passing it on to further layers. In each block a transformation is applied. The input features are first passed through a fully connected layer (FC), followed by batch normalization and a ReLU activation.

$$h_0 = \text{ReLU}(W_0X + b_0)$$

where W_0 is the weight matrix for the input layer, b_0 is the bias vector, X is the input feature matrix, and h_0 is the hidden representation output from this layer.

Residual Blocks are the core building blocks of the ResNet architecture. They allow the network to learn better representations by adding skip connections (or shortcut connections) to the network. Each residual block has two fully connected layers (FC), and each is followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation. The output of the second FC layer is then passed through a boosting transformation and combined with the input of the residual block (through a skip connection).

$$h_{l+1} = \text{ReLU}(h_l + g(h_l))$$

where h_l is the input to the block, and $g(h_l)$ is the boosting transformation applied to the output of the second fully connected layer. The boosting transformation is defined as

$$g(h_l) = \sigma(W'_l h_l + b'_l),$$

where W'_l and b'_l are the parameters of the boosting layer, and σ denotes the sigmoid activation function.

Auxiliary Layer is an intermediate output. The auxiliary layer generates a prediction based on current block. and by combining current and pervious auxiliary layers we get the weak module. This consists of a fully connected layer followed by batch normalization and a ReLU activation function:

$$h_{\text{aux}} = \text{ReLU}(W_{\text{aux}}h_l + b_{\text{aux}})$$

where W_{aux} and b_{aux} are the parameters of auxiliary layer. The output here is then added to the output of the residual block (after the boosting transformation) through another skip connection:

$$h_{l+1} = \text{ReLU}(h_{aux} + g(h_l))$$

Final Layer processes the output from the last residual block (or after all blocks) and produces the predicted class probabilities. After passing through the last residual block, the output h_L is passed through a fully connected layer to reduce the dimensions to match the number of classes.

For **classification**, a softmax activation is used to output the probabilities of the different classes:

$$\hat{y} = \text{Softmax}(W_f h_L + b_f)$$

For **regression**, a linear activation function is used to predict continuous values:

$$\hat{y} = W_f h_L + b_f$$

Where L is the number of residual blocks, and W_f , b_f are the weight and bias for the final layer.

Overall, the model is trained using the cross-entropy loss function, which is commonly used for classification tasks. For regression tasks, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) Loss is used, which computes the average of the squared differences between the predicted values and the actual values. The optimizer used is Adam optimizer.

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

I Datasets

For this project, we evaluate our model on 5 datasets.

Table 4.1: Summary of datasets used for evaluation.

HELOC [15] consists of information from real homeowners who applied for home equity lines of credit. Adult Income [13] contains demographic and personal features for income prediction. HIGGS [6] stems from particle physics Monte Carlo simulations. [34] Covertypes [13] is a multiclassification dataset, which holds cartographic information about land cells (e.g., elevation and slope). California Housing contains property information for house value estimation.

Dataset	Type	Instances	Variables	Target Variable
HELOC	Binary Classification	10,459	23	Risk Performance
Adult Income	Binary Classification	48,842	14	Income (high/low)
HIGGS	Binary Classification	11,000,000	28	Higgs signal vs. background
Covertypes	Multiclass Classification	581,012	54	Forest cover type (7 classes)
California Housing	Regression	20,640	8	House price

Data Preprocessing: Datasets were preprocessed in the same way for every machine learning model by applying zero mean, unit-variance normalization to the numerical features and an ordinal encoding to the categorical ones using the alphabetical order. The missing values were substituted with zeros for the linear regression and models based on pure neural networks since these methods cannot accept them otherwise. [7] **Hyperparameter Selection:** To do a fair evaluation, Optuna library [2] was used to tune hyperparameters. Each hyperparameter configuration was cross validated

with five folds.

Training Configuration

The experiments were done mainly using Kaggle Kernels, utilizing NVIDIA T4 GPUs due to consistent unavailability of resource with the student server. The experiments were distributed ran on over 5 different kaggle accounts and it was particularly demanding due to tuning and computational overhead. The model configurations follows the TabSurvey [7] setup.

Table 4.2: Hyperparameter tuning setup for NODE + PLE.

Hyperparameter	Search Space	Notes
Optimizer	Adam [28]	Fixed
Learning Rate	{1e-4, 1e-3}	tuned via Optuna
Batch Size	{16, 128, 256, 1024}	128 for most datasets
Early Stopping Patience	100 epochs	Applied for most datasets
Number of Layers	{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8}	Based on original NODE paper [36]
Tree Depth	{3, 4, 5, 6}	Constrained to be shallow as original NODE paper [36]
Embedding Dimensions	{16, 64}	Specific to integrating PLE
Validation Method	5-fold Cross-Validation	Defined by Tabsurvey setup [46]

II Analysis of Results

This experiment follows the setup established in Deep Neural Networks and Tabular Data: A Survey [7] to ensure a comparable benchmark. Within this setup, the baseline model NODE was modified by integrating Piecewise Linear Encoding (PLE) for numerical features, which replaced the standard scalar input processing. This model is denoted as NODE + PLE. The performance was evaluated against gradient boosted decision tree models and deep learning models.

Table 4.3: Performance metrics of NODE + PLE and GBDTs and Machine Learning Models

Method	HELOC		Adult		HIGGS		Coverttype		Cal. Housing
	Acc \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	MSE \downarrow						
Linear Model	73.0 \pm 0.0	80.1 \pm 0.1	82.5 \pm 0.2	85.4 \pm 0.2	64.1 \pm 0.0	68.4 \pm 0.0	72.4 \pm 0.0	92.8 \pm 0.0	0.528 \pm 0.008
KNN	72.2 \pm 0.0	79.0 \pm 0.1	83.2 \pm 0.2	87.5 \pm 0.2	62.3 \pm 0.1	67.1 \pm 0.0	70.2 \pm 0.1	90.1 \pm 0.2	0.421 \pm 0.009
Decision Tree	80.3 \pm 0.0	89.3 \pm 0.1	85.3 \pm 0.2	89.8 \pm 0.1	71.3 \pm 0.0	78.7 \pm 0.0	79.1 \pm 0.0	95.0 \pm 0.0	0.404 \pm 0.007
Random Forest	82.1 \pm 0.3	90.0 \pm 0.2	86.1 \pm 0.2	91.7 \pm 0.2	71.9 \pm 0.0	79.7 \pm 0.0	78.1 \pm 0.1	96.1 \pm 0.0	0.272 \pm 0.006
XGBoost	83.5 \pm 0.2	92.2 \pm 0.0	87.3 \pm 0.2	92.8 \pm 0.1	77.6\pm0.0	85.9\pm0.0	97.3\pm0.0	99.9\pm0.0	0.206 \pm 0.005
LightGBM	83.5 \pm 0.1	92.3 \pm 0.0	87.4\pm0.2	92.9\pm0.1	77.1 \pm 0.0	85.5 \pm 0.0	93.5 \pm 0.0	99.7 \pm 0.0	0.195\pm0.005
CatBoost	83.6\pm0.3	92.4\pm0.1	87.2 \pm 0.2	92.8 \pm 0.1	77.5 \pm 0.0	85.8 \pm 0.0	96.4 \pm 0.0	99.8 \pm 0.0	0.196 \pm 0.004
Model Trees	82.6 \pm 0.2	91.5 \pm 0.0	85.0 \pm 0.2	90.4 \pm 0.1	69.8 \pm 0.0	76.7 \pm 0.0	-	-	0.385 \pm 0.019
NODE + PLE	78.6 \pm 0.0	<u>72.2\pm0.0</u>	<u>86.1\pm0.5</u>	<u>91.4\pm0.4</u>	<u>73.3\pm0.0</u>	<u>81.4\pm0.0</u>	74.2 \pm 0.0	95.1 \pm 0.0	<u>0.215\pm0.009</u>
BFCN	71.0 \pm 1.1	77.6 \pm 1.3	85.1 \pm 0.5	90.9 \pm 0.4	70.6 \pm 1.1	77.7 \pm 0.9	73.4 \pm 0.2	93.2 \pm 0.6	0.277 \pm 0.017

NODE + PLE demonstrates that its performance suggests that it is highly dataset-dependent. NODE + PLE proves highly effective on the California Housing regression task, where it achieves an MSE (0.215) that is highly competitive with top-performing GBDTs like LightGBM (0.195), this shows its potential on numerical data. It also performs comparably well on the Adult dataset but is still outperformed by GBDTs. But its performance collapses on the HELOC dataset, where its AUC (72.2) is a huge outlier, falling below even simple linear models and suggesting probably a misconfiguration specific to that data. NODE + PLE on HIGGS and Coverttype even though good but not the best, which is likely due to the subsampling of datasets and reduction of embedding dimensions in other to solve the issue of memory running out during training.

Table 4.4: Performance metrics of NODE +PLE and Deep Learning Models.

Method	HELOC		Adult		HIGGS		Coverttype		Cal. Housing
	Acc \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Acc \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Acc \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Acc \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	MSE \downarrow
MLP	73.2 \pm 0.3	80.3 \pm 0.1	84.8 \pm 0.1	90.3 \pm 0.2	77.1 \pm 0.0	85.6 \pm 0.0	91.0 \pm 0.4	76.1 \pm 3.0	0.263 \pm 0.008
VIME	72.7 \pm 0.0	79.2 \pm 0.0	84.8 \pm 0.2	90.5 \pm 0.2	76.9 \pm 0.2	85.5 \pm 0.1	90.9 \pm 0.1	82.9 \pm 0.7	0.275 \pm 0.007
DeepFM	73.6 \pm 0.2	80.4 \pm 0.1	86.1 \pm 0.2	91.7 \pm 0.1	76.9 \pm 0.0	83.4 \pm 0.0	-	-	0.260 \pm 0.006
DeepGBM	78.0 \pm 0.4	84.1 \pm 0.1	84.6 \pm 0.3	90.8 \pm 0.1	74.5 \pm 0.0	83.0 \pm 0.0	-	-	0.856 \pm 0.065
NAM	73.3 \pm 0.1	80.7 \pm 0.3	83.4 \pm 0.1	86.6 \pm 0.1	53.9 \pm 0.6	55.0 \pm 1.2	-	-	0.725 \pm 0.022
Net-DNF	82.6 \pm 0.4	91.5 \pm 0.2	85.7 \pm 0.2	91.3 \pm 0.1	76.6 \pm 0.1	85.1 \pm 0.1	94.2 \pm 0.1	99.1 \pm 0.0	-
TabNet	81.0 \pm 0.1	90.0 \pm 0.1	85.4 \pm 0.2	91.1 \pm 0.1	76.5 \pm 1.3	84.9 \pm 1.4	93.1 \pm 0.2	99.4 \pm 0.0	0.346 \pm 0.007
TabTransformer	73.3 \pm 0.1	80.1 \pm 0.2	85.2 \pm 0.2	90.6 \pm 0.2	73.8 \pm 0.0	81.9 \pm 0.0	76.5 \pm 0.3	72.9 \pm 2.3	0.451 \pm 0.014
SAINT	82.1 \pm 0.3	90.7\pm0.2	86.1\pm0.3	91.6\pm0.2	79.8\pm0.0	88.3\pm0.0	96.3\pm0.1	99.8\pm0.0	0.226 \pm 0.004
RLN	73.2 \pm 0.4	80.1 \pm 0.4	81.0 \pm 1.6	75.9 \pm 8.2	71.8 \pm 0.2	79.4 \pm 0.2	77.2 \pm 1.5	92.0 \pm 0.9	0.348 \pm 0.013
STG	73.1 \pm 0.1	80.0 \pm 0.1	85.4 \pm 0.1	90.9 \pm 0.1	73.9 \pm 0.1	81.9 \pm 0.1	81.8 \pm 0.3	96.2 \pm 0.0	0.285 \pm 0.006
NODE	79.8 \pm 0.2	87.5 \pm 0.2	85.6 \pm 0.3	91.1 \pm 0.2	76.9 \pm 0.1	85.4 \pm 0.1	89.9 \pm 0.1	98.7 \pm 0.0	0.276 \pm 0.005
NODE + PLE	78.6 \pm 0.0	<u>72.2\pm0.0</u>	<u>86.1\pm0.5</u>	<u>91.4\pm0.4</u>	73.3 \pm 0.0	<u>81.4\pm0.0</u>	74.2 \pm 0.0	95.1 \pm 0.0	<u>0.215\pm0.009</u>
BFCN	71.0 \pm 1.1	77.6 \pm 1.3	85.1 \pm 0.5	90.9 \pm 0.4	70.6 \pm 1.1	77.7 \pm 0.9	73.4 \pm 0.2	93.2 \pm 0.6	0.277 \pm 0.017
BoostResNet	69.6.0 \pm 0.2	-	85.7 \pm 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-

Compared to the deep learning models,NODE + PLE achieves state of the art results on the California Housing regression task (MSE: 0.215) and competitive accuracy on the Adult dataset (Acc: 86.1). However it fails

greatly on the Heloc dataset and its results on Higgs and Covertype is good but not the best likely due to the subsampling of datasets and reduction of embedding dimensions in order to solve the issue of memory running out during training.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

We explored three different model architectures, its integration and tuning for tabular data. our model; NODE+PLE shows a significant potential of achieving competitive performance with GBDTs especially on California Housing regression task and also on the Adult dataset which validates the effectiveness of PLE. However its performance on the other datasets were not the best.

Limitations

- The results suggests that NODE + PLE's performance is subjected to the kind of dataset as its performance was inconsistent across all the datasets.
- The complexity of NODE+PLE, resulted in longer training times and higher memory requirements compared to Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDTs) and simpler MLPs. An instance is with the Cover-type and Higgs datasets which consistently run out of memory during training.
- The PLE layer relies on fixed binning strategies. In an environment where feature distributions keeps on changing, this binning may not adapt quickly resulting to a decline in model performance.

Future Works

- It is still unclear when to use NODE + PLE. large dataset or not? and what features?

- The highly invalid results of HELOC data set need to be further investigated. It suggests that PLE can memorize noise and need to be well regulated.

Bibliography

- [1] Rishabh Agarwal, Levi Melnick, Nicholas Frosst, Xuezhou Zhang, Ben Lengerich, Rich Caruana, and Geoffrey E. Hinton. Neural additive models: Interpretable machine learning with neural nets. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2021.
- [2] Takuya Akiba, Shotaro Sano, Toshihiko Yanase, Takeru Ohta, and Masanori Koyama. Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, pages 1–10, Jul. 2019.
- [3] Edesio Alcobaça, Felipe Siqueira, Adriano Rivolli, Luís P. F. Garcia, Jefferson T. Oliva, and André C. P. L. F. de Carvalho. Mfe: Towards reproducible meta-feature extraction. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 21(111):1–5, 2020.
- [4] Sercan Ö Arik and Tomas Pfister. Tabnet: Attentive interpretable tabular learning. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 35, pages 6679–6687, 2021.
- [5] Sabuhi Badirli, Xiaowen Liu, Zhao Xing, Arko Bhowmik, Khanh Doan, and Sathiya S. Keerthi. Gradient boosting neural networks: Grownnet. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2002.07971, 2020.
- [6] Pierre Baldi, Peter Sadowski, and Daniel Whiteson. Searching for exotic particles in high-energy physics with deep learning. *Nature Communications*, 5(1):1–9, Sep. 2014.
- [7] R.V. Borisov, T. Leemann, K. Seßler, J. Haug, M. Pawelczyk, and G. Kasneci. Deep neural networks and tabular data: A survey. 2022.
- [8] Tom Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared D. Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, Pranav Shyam, Girish

- Sastry, Amanda Askell, et al. Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33:1877–1901, 2020.
- [9] Tianqi Chen and Carlos Guestrin. Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016.
- [10] Corinna Cortes, Xavier Gonzalvo, Vitaly Kuznetsov, Mehryar Mohri, and Scott Yang. Adanet: Adaptive structural learning of artificial neural networks. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 874–883. PMLR, 2017.
- [11] Alexey Dosovitskiy, Lucas Beyer, Alexander Kolesnikov, Dirk Weissenborn, Xiaohua Zhai, Thomas Unterthiner, Mostafa Dehghani, Matthias Minderer, Georg Heigold, Sylvain Gelly, et al. An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2021.
- [12] James Dougherty, Ron Kohavi, and Mehran Sahami. Supervised and unsupervised discretization of continuous features. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, pages 194–202, 1995.
- [13] Dheeru Dua and Casey Graff. Uci machine learning repository. Online, 2017.
- [14] S. Elsayed, D. Thyssens, A. Rashed, H. S. Jomaa, and L. Schmidt-Thieme. Do we really need deep learning models for time series forecasting? *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2101.02118, 2021.
- [15] FICO. Home equity line of credit (heloc) dataset, 2019. Accessed: Jun. 15, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://community.fico.com/s/explainable-machine-learning-challenge>.
- [16] Yoav Freund and Robert E. Schapire. A decision-theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*, 55(1):119–139, 1997.
- [17] Jerome H. Friedman. Greedy function approximation: a gradient boosting machine. *Annals of Statistics*, 29(5):1189–1232, 2001.
- [18] Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, and Aaron Courville. *Deep Learning*. MIT Press, 2016.

- [19] Yury Gorishniy, Ivan Rubachev, and Artem Babenko. On embeddings for numerical features in tabular deep learning. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 35, pages 24991–25004, 2022.
- [20] Yury Gorishniy, Ivan Rubachev, Valentin Khrulkov, and Artem Babenko. Revisiting deep learning models for tabular data. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 34, pages 18932–18943, 2021.
- [21] Lucien Grinsztajn, Edouard Oyallon, and Gaël Varoquaux. Why do tree-based models still outperform deep learning on typical tabular data? *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35:507–520, 2022.
- [22] Xiaojuan Qi Ruigang Yang Gao Huang Hao Li, Hong Zhang. Improved techniques for training adaptive deep networks. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2019.
- [23] Xiang He, Ke Zhao, and Xiaowen Chu. Automl: A survey of the state-of-the-art. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 212:106622, 2021.
- [24] Furong Huang, Jordan Ash, and Robert Schapire. Learning deep resnet blocks sequentially using boosting theory. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2018.
- [25] Gao Huang, Yu Sun, Zhuang Liu, Daniel Sedra, and Kilian Q. Weinberger. Multi-scale dense convolutional networks for efficient prediction. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1703.09844, 2017.
- [26] Arlind Kadra, Marius Lindauer, Frank Hutter, and Josif Grabocka. Well-tuned simple nets excel on tabular datasets. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 34, 2021.
- [27] Guolin Ke, Qi Meng, Thomas Finley, Taifeng Wang, Wei Chen, Weidong Ma, Qiwei Ye, and Tie-Yan Liu. Lightgbm: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree. 2017.
- [28] Diederik P. Kingma and Jimmy Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980*, 2014.
- [29] Ron Kohavi and Mehran Sahami. Error-based and entropy-based discretization of continuous features. In *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD)*, pages 114–119. AAAI Press, 1996.

- [30] Roman Levin, Valeriia Cherepanova, Avi Schwarzschild, Arpit Bansal, C Bayan Bruss, Tom Goldstein, Andrew Gordon Wilson, and Micah Goldblum. Transfer learning with deep tabular models. In *International Conference on Learning Representations, 2023*.
- [31] J. Li, Y. Li, X. Xiang, S.-T. Xia, S. Dong, and Y. Cai. Tnt: An interpretable tree-network-tree learning framework using knowledge distillation. *Entropy*, 22(11):1203, 2020.
- [32] Duncan McElfresh, Saurabh Khandagale, Jose Valverde, Chaitanya V. Prasad, Goutham Ramakrishnan, Micah Goldblum, and Colin White. When do neural nets outperform boosted trees on tabular data? In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 36, pages 76336–76369, 2023.
- [33] D. Medvedev and A. D’yakonov. New properties of the data distillation method when working with tabular data. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2010.09839, 2020.
- [34] Christopher Z. Mooney. *Monte Carlo Simulation*. SAGE, Newbury Park, CA, USA, 1997.
- [35] Ben Peters, Vlad Niculae, and André FT Martins. Sparse sequence-to-sequence models. In *Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, pages 1504–1519. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2019.
- [36] Sergei Popov, Stanislav Morozov, and Artem Babenko. Neural oblivious decision ensembles for deep learning on tabular data. In *International Conference on Learning Representations, 2020*.
- [37] Sergey Popov, Stanislav Morozov, and Andrey Babenko. Neural oblivious decision ensembles for deep learning on tabular data. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1909.06312, 2019.
- [38] Liudmila Prokhorenkova, Gleb Gusev, Aleksandr Vorobev, Anna V. Dorogush, and Andrey Gulin. Catboost: unbiased boosting with categorical features. 2018.
- [39] Nasim Rahaman, Aristide Baratin, Devansh Arpit, Felix Draxler, Min Lin, Fred A. Hamprecht, Yoshua Bengio, and Aaron Courville. On the spectral bias of neural networks. In *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, pages 5301–5310. PMLR, 2019.

- [40] D. Roschewitz, M.-A. Hartley, L. Corinzia, and M. Jaggi. Ifedavg: Interpretable data-interoperability for federated learning. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2107.06580, 2021.
- [41] Ivan Rubachev, Artem Alekberov, Yury Gorishniy, and Artem Babenko. Revisiting pretraining objectives for tabular deep learning. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2207.03208, 2022.
- [42] Debo Sahoo, Quang Pham, Jing Lu, and Steven C. Hoi. Online deep learning: Learning deep neural networks on the fly. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1711.03705, 2017.
- [43] Jürgen Schmidhuber. Deep learning in neural networks: An overview. *Neural Networks*, 61:85–117, 2015.
- [44] Shai Shalev-Shwartz. Selfieboost: A boosting algorithm for deep learning. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2014.
- [45] Xiang Shi, Johannes Mueller, Nicholas Erickson, Ming Li, and Alexander Smola. Multimodal automl on structured tables with text fields. In *8th ICML Workshop on Automated Machine Learning (AutoML)*, 2021.
- [46] Ravid Shwartz-Ziv and Amit Armon. Tabular data: Deep learning is not all you need. 2021.
- [47] Matthew Tancik, Pratul P. Srinivasan, Ben Mildenhall, Sara Fridovich-Keil, Nithin Raghavan, Utkarsh Singhal, Ravi Ramamoorthi, Jonathan T. Barron, and Ren Ng. Fourier features let networks learn high frequency functions in low dimensional domains. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2020.
- [48] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is all you need. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, pages 5998–6008, 2017.
- [49] Le Yang, Xiaoyang Huang, Hao Zhang, Yu Wang, Zhiwei Liu, and Gao Huang. Resolution adaptive networks for efficient inference. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.

- [50] Hanting Yu, Hao Li, Gang Hua, Gao Huang, and Honghui Shi. Boosted dynamic neural networks. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2023.
- [51] Hanting Yu, Hao Li, Gang Hua, Gao Huang, and Honghui Shi. Boosted dynamic neural networks. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 37, pages 10989–10997, 2023.
- [52] Shuai Zhang, Lina Yao, Aixin Sun, and Yi Tay. Deep learning based recommender system: A survey and new perspectives. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 52(1):1–38, 2019.